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Research Article

DETERMINING FACTORS FOR THE PREVALENCE OF ANEMIA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE.¹Dr Sana Eman,²Dr Abubakar Obaid,³Dr Muhammad Huzaifa Javaid.¹MBBS, Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi.²MBBS, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat.³MBBS, Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad.

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Abstract:

The most common cause of anemia around the globe is iron deficiency anemia. Pregnant women, children and women of reproductive age are more prone to get anemia. Child mortality and morbidity is linked with maternal anemia such as an increased risk of miscarriage, stillbirth, and prematurity and low birth weight of the baby. In developed countries there is approximately 20% of perinatal mortality and maternal mortality are contributing factor of iron deficiency anemia. It was stated that in 2005 there were 1.63 billion people were affected by anemia around the world. While in 2011 it was estimated that the global prevalence of anemia among pregnant women is about 38%, and non-pregnant women is about 29%, and for all women of reproductive age is about 29%. As compared with low- and middle-income countries the prevalence of anemia among non-pregnant and pregnant women was seen low in high-income countries.

. This study found that about 44% of the women of reproductive age were anemic. It indicates that anemia could be serious public health concern. Current study has given the statistics of prevalence of anemia is high as compared to previous literature it highlights the need to reconsider the existing nutritional policy. Obese was seen less likely to be anemic as compared to women with underweight who were having higher prevalence. Poor nutritional status is basic reason of both, anemia and lower BM. increasing the risk of developing anemia may result in Poor diet quality and lower bioavailability of dietary iron. Mobilization of community health workers and volunteers can be a strategic measure to reach a large section of adolescents including women of reproductive age. For the recommendation of anemia surveillance and interventions programs specific to targeted groups and high-risk populations. More studies are required to actually determine the causing factors associated with anemia.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Sana Eman,**

MBBS, Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

A condition where the numbers of red blood cells are not sufficient enough to meet the physiological need of the body is known as anemia or low concentration of hemoglobin. The most common cause of anemia around the globe is iron deficiency anemia. Pregnant women, children and women of reproductive age are more prone to get anemia. Child mortality and morbidity is linked with maternal anemia such as an increased risk of miscarriage, stillbirth, and prematurity and low birth weight of the baby. In developed countries there is approximately 20% of perinatal mortality and maternal mortality are contributing factor of iron deficiency anemia. It was stated that in 2005 there were 1.63 billion people were affected by anemia around the world. While in 2011 it was estimated that the global prevalence of anemia among pregnant women is about 38%, and non-pregnant women is about 29%, and for all women of reproductive age is about 29%. As compared with low- and middle-income countries the prevalence of anemia among non-pregnant and pregnant women was seen low in high-income countries.

The World Health Organization (WHO) classified the public health significance of anemia based on the prevalence estimated from blood levels of hemoglobin (normal, <4.9%; mild. 5.0-19.9%; moderate, 20.0-39.9% and severe >40.0%). Causing factors could be age, sex, residential elevation (altitude), smoking behavior, and pregnancy status influence hemoglobin concentration. However an association was found between immunologic disease progression and increased risk of AIDS-related death due to anemia. On the other hand studies have shown that use of hormonal contraceptives have a potential protective effect against anemia. The aim of the study is to evaluate the prevalence of anemia among reproductive women and the causing factors associated with it.

STUDY DESIGN:

It was a cross-sectional study in which women were included more than age 15 to 49 years. Socio-demographic data was collected from the participants recruited in the study. For this study, BMI was categorized as underweight (less than 18.5 kg/m²), normal (18.5– 24.9 kg/m²), overweight (25.0–29.9 kg/m²), and obese (>30.0 kg/m²). For regression analysis, overweight and obese categories were merged into a single category as overweight/obese. The data on anthropometric measures (height and weight) and hemoglobin concentration was collected. An informed consent was signed after explaining the purpose of the study. Frequencies and proportions

(weighted) were reported. Mean and standard deviations were used for continuous variables. Chi-square test (χ^2) or Fisher's exact was used to assess the frequency distribution and the relationship between independent variables and anemia status.

RESULTS:

Total 114 participants aged 15–49 years (mean [\pm SD] age, 29.2 years [\pm 9.6]) were included in the study. High prevalence of anemia was found between the age group of 15-24 years. 33% had completed their secondary education. 41% belonged to upper class and 52% were under middle class. About one-third of the women (33%) had < 3 children. Prevalence of anemia the mean (\pm SD) hemoglobin level concentration was 12.1 g/dl (\pm 1.4).

An overall prevalence of any anemia among women aged 15–49 years was 43%. Specifically, mild, moderate, and severe anemia was found in 331%, 7%, and 0.3% of the women, respectively. The prevalence of anemia decreased with the increase in both the age group, and age at first birth among women who had first birth >25 years. The high prevalence of anemia was seen among women living in rural area (41%), having secondary education (42%), unemployed (45%), of middle-class family (48%), having wells as the sources of drinking water (53%), postpartum amenorrhoeic (48%), had birth in the past three years (42%), breastfeeding (41%), not using any contraceptive methods (40%), underweight (41%), and non-smoker (43%). Overweight/obese women had reduced odds of developing anemia compared to women with normal body weight. Factors such as age, ethnicity, household wealth status, fertility status, having a birth in the past three years, and breastfeeding did not reveal any significant association with the risk of developing anemia despite their significant relationship in the univariate analysis.

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of anemia was decreased to 12% between 1995 and 2014 which demonstrate that it could be due to prevention and management. No significant association was found between anemia and women's age. On the other hand some studies have shown that there was an association found between developed countries and anemia. This prevalence was found to be decreased with the increase in age. The high prevalence of anemia in younger age could be due to negative effects of low dietary iron intake and additional demand for iron imposed by iron loss during menstruation, pregnancy, and lactation. The rate of anemia was higher in age less than 20 years who gave the first birth. A

confounding reason was seen in teenage pregnancy that could be possible reason of high prevalence of anemia. Similarly, the likelihood of anemia was found to be increased with multiple pregnancies. Major risk factors for mother and infant are multiple pregnancies coupled with low-quality diets and parasitic infections. Lactation increases the nutritional demand which also attribute to the high prevalence of anemia. This is why the prevalence of anemia was found to be high among poor and rural women.

Though poverty affected women's nutritional status, this study found no significant differences between anemia and household wealth status, consistent with another study from Bangladesh. Inability of women take a decision regarding the type and quantity of food was strongly linked with domestic violence. Nutritional deficiencies are caused with as a withholding of food, as a form of abuse against women which also results in anemia. Women were less likely to report violence against them because of fear of husband or some family members, fear of losing family prestige as well as economic support from the family.

First, this study did not differentiate between different types of anemia because many other factors such as vitamin B-12, folate, ferritin, and parasitic infections were not included in this study. Finally, due to the cross-sectional design of the study, it was not possible to determine the cause-effect relationship between the predictor variables and anemia; further prospective researches are required to understand this relationship.

CONCLUSION:

This study has indicated the factors associated with the prevalence of anemia. It is quite evident from the study findings that the general health status of the women of reproductive age needs substantial improvement. This study found that about 44% of the women of reproductive age were anemic. It indicates that anemia could be serious public health concern. Current study has given the statistics of prevalence of anemia is high as compared to previous literature it highlights the need to reconsider the existing nutritional policy. Obese was seen less likely to be anemic as compared to women with underweight who were having higher prevalence. Poor nutritional status is basic reason of both, anemia and lower BM. increasing the risk of developing anemia may result in Poor diet quality and lower bioavailability of dietary iron. Mobilization of community health workers and volunteers can be a strategic measure to reach a large section of adolescents including women

of reproductive age. For the recommendation of anemia surveillance and interventions programs specific to targeted groups and high-risk populations. More studies are required to actually determine the causing factors associated with anemia.

REFERENCES:

1. The World Health Organization; Haemoglobin concentrations for the diagnosis of anemia and assessment of severity. Geneva: WHO; 2011. [1 March 2019]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/vmnis/indicators/haemoglobin/en/>. [Google Scholar]
2. McLean E, Cogswell M, Egli I, Wojdyla D, de Benoist B. Worldwide prevalence of anaemia, WHO Vitamin and Mineral Nutrition Information System, 1993–2005. *Public Health Nutr.* 2009;12:444–54. 10.1017/S1368980008002401 [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
3. World Health Organization. The global prevalence of anaemia in 2011. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2015. [21 May 2019]. [Google Scholar]
4. World Health Organization. Global Nutrition Targets 2025: Anemia Policy Brief Geneva: WHO; 2014. [10 March 2019]. Available from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/148556/WHO_NMH_NHD_14.4_eng.pdf?ua=1. [Google Scholar]
5. World Health Organization. The World Health Report 2002: Reducing Risks, Promoting Healthy Life: WHO; 2002. [8 March 2019]. Available from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/42510/WHR_2002.pdf?sequence=1. [Google Scholar]
6. Stevens GA, Finucane MM, De-Regil LM, Paciorek CJ, Flaxman SR, Branca F, et al. Global, regional, and national trends in haemoglobin concentration and prevalence of total and severe anaemia in children and pregnant and non-pregnant women for 1995–2011: a systematic analysis of population-representative data. *The Lancet Glob Health.* 2013;1(1):e16–e25. 10.1016/S2214-109X(13)70001-9 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
7. Horton S, Ross J. The economics of iron deficiency. *Food Policy.* 2003;28:51–75. 10.1016/S0306-9192(02)00070-2. [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
8. Balarajan Y, Ramakrishnan U, Özaltin E, Shankar AH, Subramanian SV. Anaemia in low-income and middle-income countries. *The Lancet.* 2011;378(9809):2123–35.

- 10.1016/S0140-6736(10)62304-5. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
9. Harding KL, Aguayo VM, Namirembe G, Webb P. Determinants of anemia among women and children in Nepal and Pakistan: An analysis of recent national survey data. *Matern Child Nutr.* 2018;14(S4):e12478 10.1111/mcn.12478 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 10. Lee J-O, Lee JH, Ahn S, Kim JW, Chang H, Kim YJ, et al. Prevalence and risk factors for iron deficiency anemia in the Korean population: results of the fifth Korea National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *J Korean Med Sci.* 2014;29:224–9. 10.3346/jkms.2014.29.2.224 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 11. Adamu AL, Crampin A, Kayuni N, Amberbir A, Koole O, Phiri A, et al. Prevalence and risk factors for anemia severity and type in Malawian men and women: urban and rural differences. *Popul Health Metr.* 2017;15:12–. 10.1186/s12963-017-0128-2 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 12. Balarajan YS, Fawzi WW, Subramanian SV. Changing patterns of social inequalities in anaemia among women in India: cross-sectional study using nationally representative data. *BMJ Open.* 2013;3(3):e002233 10.1136/bmjopen-2012-002233 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 13. Ackerson LK, Subramanian SV. Domestic violence and chronic malnutrition among women and children in India. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2008;167(10):1188–96. 10.1093/aje/kwn049 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 14. Bethony J, Brooker S, Albonico M, Geiger SM, Loukas A, Diemert D, et al. Soil-transmitted helminth infections: ascariasis, trichuriasis, and hookworm. *The Lancet.* 2006;367:1521–32. 10.1016/S0140-6736(06)68653-4. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 15. Menendez C, Fleming AF, Alonso PL. Malaria-related Anaemia. *Parasitol Today.* 2000;16:469–76. 10.1016/S0169-4758(00)01774-9. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 16. O'Brien ME, Kupka R, Msamanga GI, Saathoff E, Hunter DJ, Fawzi WW. Anemia Is an Independent Predictor of Mortality and Immunologic Progression of Disease Among Women With HIV in Tanzania. *J Acquir Immune Defic Syndr.* 2005;40 10.1097/01.qai.0000166374.16222.a2 [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 17. Haile ZT, Kingori C, Teweldeberhan AK, Chavan B. The relationship between history of hormonal contraceptive use and iron status among women in Tanzania: A population-based study. *Sex Reprod Healthc.* 2017;13:97–102. 10.1016/j.srhc.2017.07.003 [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 18. Chalise B, Aryal KK, Mehta RK, Dhimal M, Sapkota F, Mehata S, et al. Prevalence and correlates of anemia among adolescents in Nepal: Findings from a nationally representative cross-sectional survey. *PLoS One.* 2018;13:e0208878 10.1371/journal.pone.0208878 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 19. Singh P, Khan S, Ansari M, Mittal R. Anemia among adolescent Girls and Boys attending Outpatients and Inpatient facilities in far-western part of Nepal. *Ibnosina Journal of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences.* 2013;5:330–34. [Google Scholar]
 20. Baral KP, Onta SR. Prevalence of anemia amongst adolescents in Nepal: a community based study in rural and urban areas of Morang District. *Nepal Med Coll J.* 2009;11:179–82. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 21. Sinha AK, Karki GMS, Karna KK. Prevalence of Anemia amongst Adolescents in Biratnagar, Morang District Nepal. *Int J Pharma Bio Sci.* 2012;3:1077–81. [Google Scholar]
 22. Dreyfuss ML, Stoltzfus RJ, Shrestha JB, Pradhan EK, LeClerq SC, Khatry SK, et al. Hookworms, Malaria and Vitamin A Deficiency Contribute to Anemia and Iron Deficiency among Pregnant Women in the Plains of Nepal. *Journal Nutr.* 2000;130:2527–36. 10.1093/jn/130.10.2527 [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
 23. Chandyo RK, Strand TA, Ulvik RJ, Adhikari RK, Ulak M, Dixit H, et al. Prevalence of iron deficiency and anemia among healthy women of reproductive age in Bhaktapur, Nepal. *European Journal Of Clinical Nutrition.* 2006;61:262 10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602508 [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]